

Aminocarbonylation with Ethyl Carbamate : An access to Nitrogen Heterocycles[†]

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In course of synthesis of some quinazolones (1, 2, 3) of Rutaceae^{1,2} by the reaction of appropriately substituted anilides (4, 5, 6) with ethylcarbamate (7) in boiling xylene in presence of P₂O₅, our attention was drawn to the synthesis of quinazolones appropriate benzamide derivatives by Meyer and Wagner³ as well as by Chakraborty *et al.*⁴. Further, Gattermann⁵ in 1888 showed that polar

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|----|--|---|--|---|--|
| 4 | R ₁ = H, | 7 | | 1 | R ₁ = CH ₃ , Ph, |
| | R ₂ = COCH ₃ , Ph, | | | 2 | R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = OH, Ph |
| | R ₃ = H | | | 3 | R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = H |
| 4a | R ₁ = H, R ₂ = COCH ₃ , Ph, R ₃ = CONH ₂ , | | | | |
| 5 | R ₁ = OH, R ₂ = COCH ₃ , Ph, R ₃ = H | | | | |
| 5a | R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = COCH ₃ , Ph, R ₃ = CONH ₂ , | | | | |
| 6 | R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = CHO, R ₃ = H | | | | |

aromatic substrates like mesitylene (9) could be amidated to 10 with carbamyl chloride under Friedel-Crafts conditions.

In consideration of the above facts, previously we showed⁵ that appropriate anilides (4, 5, 6) could be C-aminocarbonylated at *ortho*-position (4a, 5a, 6a) with ethylcarbamate (7) under AlCl₃ catalysed condition. This could be cyclised to quinazolone with P₂O₅. In course of this reaction, we further showed that under Friedel-Craft's condition polar aromatic substrates (9, 11-13) could be C-aminocarbonylated to the corresponding amides (8, 10, 14-16). Evidently our method provides a convenient modification of Gattermann's amidation reaction.

The aminocarbonylation involving the transfer of carbamyl group (CONH₂) from phosphate ester of carbamic acid (17) is a well known biochemical process by which one of the amino acids of the urea cycle, L-ornithin (18), is aminocarbonylated under enzyme mediation (*ornithin trans carbamylase*).

Through other two steps as shown above, the ornithin is regenerated. On the other hand, the

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biological carbamyl phosphate transfer with the phosphate ester of carbamic acid results in the *N*-aminocarbonylation of aspartic acid⁸ (23). The carboamylated aspartic acid (24) under enzyme mediation gives rise to dihydroorotic acid (25), the key intermediate in the biosynthesis of pyrimidine nucleotides.

The overall mechanistic process in such enzyme mediated C-N bond formation involves the nucleophilic attack of the aminonitrogen on the carbon of the carbamyl phosphate and subsequent elimination

of the ester function. Such displacement mechanism has also been envisaged⁹ in the reactions of higher alcohols with 7. The nucleophilic attack of the aminonitrogen on the carbon of the ethylcarbamate (7) has been demonstrated by us during the formation of phenyl urea (27) from aniline (26) under Friedel-Crafts' condition as well as the formation of quinoxalinedione (28) from anthranilic acid.

The synthesis of pyrimidine and of quinazolones *via* aminocarbonylation of different substrates with esters of carbamic acid by nucleophilic attack on the carbon of the carbamic acid, prompted us to undertake further studies on C-aminocarbonylation with cyclohexanone, as they provide an appropriate nucleophile under the reaction conditions. In the present communication, we report our results on C-aminocarbonylation with cyclohexanone (30), 4-methyl cyclohexanone (31) and 2-methyl cyclohexanone (32) with (7) under Friedel-Crafts' condition.

Cyclohexanone (30) and ethyl carbamate (7) in a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 120-60°) on heating for six hours in presence of AlCl₃ furnished compounds 33 and 34. The compound (33) C₁₈H₂₄ (M⁺240) m.p. 231-32°, showed λ_{max} at 229 and 269 nm with log ε 4.12 and 2.45, and ν_{max} at 1652, 1580 and 1440 cm⁻¹. The mass spectral peak at *m/z* 77, of 33 could be reconciled with the presence of a phenyl ring in it. From all these data, 33 was characterised as *S*-dodecahydrotriphenylene^{1,2} previously obtained by reacting cyclohexanone

with concentrated HCl, H₂SO₄ or Lewis acids, like ZnCl₂, though its formation by boiling in presence of AlCl₃ has not been reported.

The compound 34, C₁₈H₁₇NO (M⁺203), m.p. 290°, was insoluble in dilute HCl but soluble in concentrated H₂SO₄ and gave a red colouration with FeCl₃ solution. The uv spectrum of this compound at λ_{max} 231 and 301 nm with log 4.57 and 4.68 like pyridone¹⁰ (λ_{max} 224 and 293 nm with ε 7230 and 5900, respectively, vapour phase¹¹ λ_{max} 295 nm) and *N*-methyl pyridone (λ_{max} 226 and 297 with ε 6100 and 5700, together with irband at ν_{max} 1630-40 (NH), 1550 and 1270 cm⁻¹ (C-N and NH) support the presence of pyridone fragment in 34. The absence of band at 3300 cm⁻¹ region does not show the absence of a pyridone system, for which the band at 1650 cm⁻¹ region is more characteristic¹². The nmr data of 34 showed signals at δ 11.9 (1H, CO-NH) 2.5-2.7 (4H, m, benzylic protons), 2.3-2.5 (4H, m, benzylic protons) and 1.65-1.95 (8H, aliphatic protons). The highly deshielded signal at δ 11.9 could be attributed to the NH proton of the α-pyridone system. This could be explained due to facile

lactam-lactim (34-35) tautomerism. The mass spectral data showed the peak at *m/z* 203. The significant peak at *m/z* 174 (M-28-1) could be presented by 36 similar to those recorded in case of phenanthridones.

¹³C nmr spectrum of the compound with signals at δ 215.14 (C=O) and 163.5 (C attached to the nitrogen) also support the proposed structure 34 for the nitrogenous product. This has been confirmed by dehydrogenation of 34 to phenanthridone (37), m.p. 293°. 4-Methylcyclohexanone (31)

under above experimental conditions furnished a nitrogenous compound, $C_{15}H_{21}NO$ (M^+231). The positive $FeCl_3$ reaction and the uv spectrum, λ_{max} 250 and 303 with $\log \epsilon$ 4.7 and 4.3 were suggestive of the pyridone, structure like **34**. This has also been supported by its ir spectrum, ν_{max} 1625-35, 1550 and 1275 cm^{-1} . The pmr data of **38** showed signal at δ 12.1 (**38a**; 1H, lactam-lactim tautomer) and 2.30-3.13 (m, 8H, benzylic proton), 1.6-2.25 (m, 6H, 4-methylene protons together with 2-methine protons). Like **34** its mass spectral data show significant peak at m/z 201 which could be represented by **38b**. The dehydrogenation of **38** to 5,9-dimethylphenanthridone (**39**) confirmed the structure of **38**.

The formation of *S*-dodecahydrotripheylene by acid catalysis is considered to be an aldol type reaction of cyclohexanone wherein one molecule attacks the reactive methylene of the other. The idea has been substantiated by the isolation of the species (**40**, **41**)¹⁸.

Evidently the $AlCl_3$ catalysed enolised¹⁴ species could be assumed to be C-aminocarbonylated to **42** which reacts with another molecule of cyclohexanone to give the intermediate **43** which readily gives rise to the stabler species **34**. Such ready transformation to a stabler species is reminiscent of the enamine chemistry¹⁵.

The direct evidence for the formation of the aminocarbonylated cyclohexanone species has come from the experiments with 2-methylcyclohexanone when nitrogenous compound $C_9H_{14}N_2O_3$ (M^+198), λ_{max} 250 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.12) (**44**) was isolated. The ir spectrum of the compound showed bands at 3150, 3050, 1720 and 1656 cm^{-1} showing the presence

of amide system and six-membered ketone. One of the amide nitrogen is chelated (ν_{max} 3050 cm^{-1}). The pmr data showed bands for NH protons at δ 7.85 and 7.6 (2H), while the other signal was at 5.23 (2H, broad). 2-Methylcyclohexanone gives rise to two enolate ions¹⁶, **45**, **46** of which **45** is preferentially attacked giving rise to the intermediate monoamide after which amidation of the second enolate takes place resulting into **44**. The situation is very similar to the alkylation of unsymmetrical ketones resulting into isomeric products. This amide perhaps cannot react further to yield pyridone derivatives due to stereoelectronic factors. The structure **44** was also supported by its mass spectral fragmentation.

Above experiments show that under appropriate conditions cyclohexanones may be aminocarbonylated and in some cases transient amide immediately reacts to yield the heterocyclic system.

From the data and discussions it is evident that aminocarbonylation with esters of carbamic acid appears to be a convenient method for *N*-heterocyclisation whereby an additional nitrogen is inserted from the carbamyl group. Aminocarbonylation by ethylcarbamate provides a laboratory analogy of biological aminocarbonylation with carbamyl phosphate.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Analytical samples were analysed after drying over P_2O_5 *in vacuo* at 80° for 24 h.

Attempted aminocarbonylation of cyclohexanone with ethyl carbamate :

Preparation of octahydro phenanthridone (34) : A mixture of cyclohexanone (0.3 mol) and ethylcarbamate (0.3 mol) in dry benzene was diluted with petroleum ether to 50 ml. To the reaction mixture anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (0.33 mol) was added portionwise in cold. After careful shaking the reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h, cooled, acidified with cold dilute HCl and neutralized with $NaHCO_3$. The solution was extracted with ethyl acetate (3×150 ml). After making the solution acid-free and dry, the solvent was removed when an oily mass was obtained from which crystals were obtained after cooling. The crystals obtained after filtration melted at 231-32° after crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°)(18%, lit.¹⁹ highest yield 13%). This was characterised as *S*-dodecahydrotripheylene,

$C_{15}H_{24}$ (lit. m.p. 230°) (Found: C, 90.20; H, 10.0). $C_{15}H_{24}$ requires C, 90.0; H, 10.0%.

The oily liquid after dilution with chloroform (35 ml) yielded yellowish crystals, which on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished a homogenous nitrogenous compound (70%), m.p. 292-3° (Found: C, 76.79; H 8.22; N, 6.70. $C_{15}H_{17}NO$ requires C, 76.8; H, 8.37; N, 6.89%); ^{13}C nmr 215.14, 163.55, 148.78, 138.01, 118.44, 78.50, 26.78, 26.19, 23.24, 22.61, 22.12, 21.75 and 21.54.

Dehydrogenation of octahydrophenanthridone to phenanthridone (37): Octahydrophenanthridone (30 mg) mixed with catalytic amounts of Pd/C in *p*-cymene (2.5 ml). The mixture was heated in a sealed tube at 220° for 5 h. The mixture diluted with chloroform, filtered. The filtrate on concentration gave a colourless solid which on crystallisation from benzene furnished homogenous colourless crystals of phenanthridone, m.p. 293° (lit. m.p. 293°); ν_{max} 3400, 1670, 1640, 1615, 1560 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} 224, 230, 236.5, 258, 269, 308, 321, 335.5 nm with log ϵ 5.05, 5.22, 5.03, 4.12, 4.25, 3.99, 3.81, 3.86, 3.81.

Synthesis of 5,9-dimethyl-octahydrophenanthridone (38): A mixture of 4-methylcyclohexanone (0.3 mol) and ethyl carbamate (0.3 mol) in minimum quantity of benzene was diluted to 50 ml by adding high boiling petroleum ether (b.p. 120-60°). $AlCl_3$ (0.33 mol) was added in portion and the mixture was refluxed at 170-190° for 6 h. Working up of the reaction products gave an oily mass from which colourless crystals of 5,9-dimethyloctahydrophenanthridone (36) was obtained after repeated crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether, (70%), m.p. 260° (Found: C, 77.95; H, 9.09; N, 6.08. $C_{15}H_{21}NO$ requires C, 77.92; H, 9.12; N, 6.06%); ν_{max} 1625-35 and 1550 cm^{-1} ; δ 12.1 (1H), 2.30-2.25 (8H), 1.16 (6H), 1.16 (3H) and 1.08 (3H); m/z 231 (M^+), 230 (69%), 216, 202 and 201.

Dehydrogenation of 5,9-dimethyloctahydrophenanthridone to 5,9-dimethylphenanthridone (39): 5,9-Dimethyl-octahydrophenanthridone (50 mg) was mixed with catalytic amounts of Pd/C and a few drops of *p*-cymene added. The reaction mixture was then heated at 220° for 15 h in a sealed tube. Working up of the reaction mixture give a homogenous compound which was characterised as 5,9-dimethylphenanthridone m.p. 256° (lit. m.p. 256°) (Found: C, 80.74; H, 5.80; N, 6.30. $C_{15}H_{15}NO$ requires C, 80.71; H, 5.82; N, 6.27%).

Amino carbonylation of 2-methyl cyclohexanone with ethylcarbamate, formation of 44: To a solution

of 2-methylcyclohexanone (0.3 mol) and ethyl carbamate (0.3 mol) in dry benzene and high boiling petroleum ether (45 ml). $AlCl_3$ (0.33 mol) was added in portions and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h at 200-210° (bath temp.). After work up as above a colourless solid was obtained after repeated crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (62%), m.p. 216-17° (Found: C, 54.76; H, 7.24; N, 14.32. $C_9H_{14}N_2O_3$ requires C, 54.54; H, 7.07; N, 14.14%); ν_{max} 3150, 3050, 1720 and 1665 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} 250 nm with log ϵ 4.12; δ 7.85, 7.6 ($CONH_2$), 5.25 ($CONH_2$), 1.88-2.33, 1.47 (3H); m/z 198 (M^+), M-18 (100%), 65, 152, 137, 126, 109 and 94.

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